

From Cure to Curse: The Rise and Fall of Bilingual Education Programs in the Netherlands

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For about 35 years, two types of bilingual education programs have been offered to ethnic minorities in the Netherlands. The first are the bilingual reception models, which have been applied only in a few schools. The second, Mother Tongue Instruction (MTI), was more widespread and took up as much as 10% of the time spent at school. The focus in this paper is on MTI. As MTI has been abolished as of 2004, this chapter bears the character of an evaluation of the policy developments, their implementation, and effects. The following text provides an overview of policy developments with regard to MTI. It takes a closer look at the arguments on which that policy was based and presents arguments held against this policy. Subsequent paragraphs outline major results of Dutch evaluation studies of bilingual education. The paper concludes with some observations about why, given the unfavorable framework, bilingual education in the Netherlands could not become a success story.

1. Ethnic Minorities in the Netherlands

Since World War II, various groups of immigrants have come to the Netherlands, mainly for political and economic reasons. They comprise immigrants from the former Dutch colonies, i.e. the Dutch East Indies (largely Indo-Europeans), the Moluccas, Surinam, and the Netherlands Antilles. As a result of their ties with the (former) motherland, these immigrants were already somewhat acquainted with the Dutch language and culture.

Primarily during the early 1960s, so-called foreign or guest workers arrived from the Mediterranean countries, e.g. Italy, Spain, Portugal, Greece, Yugoslavia, Turkey, and Morocco. Due to family reunification and the immigration of spouses, there has been a continuous influx of immigrants ever since, particularly coming from Turkey and Morocco. One characteristic these immigrants have in common is their low level of education. Furthermore, their languages and cultures differ considerably from the Dutch. This is true particularly for the Turks and Moroccans.

Refugees and asylum seekers who arrived from Eastern Europe, Latin-America, Asia, Africa, and the Middle-East, are a very diverse and ever-changing group, both in terms of languages and culture.

Furthermore, there are immigrants from Western countries, such as Belgium, Germany, the UK, and the USA, who usually have a middle or higher socio-economic status.

Only some immigrant groups are the targets of an ethnic minority policy. Immigrants from the Dutch East Indies are excluded from this policy as are immigrants from Western countries. In essence the ethnic minority policy is aimed at those immigrants (and their descendants) with a low socio-economic status. Depending on which criterion is applied, the percentage of people resident in the Netherlands who belong to ethnic minorities (henceforth: minorities) varies from 7 to 19 per cent. Based on the 'country of birth' (of the individuals and their parents), in 2003 the largest minority groups in the Netherlands were of Turkish (341,000), Surinamese (321,000), Moroccan (295,000), and Antillean (129,000) origin, out of a total Dutch population of 16 million (Tweede Kamer 2003). A large share of the minority population lives in the major cities. On average they are relatively young. As a consequence, in cities such as Amsterdam, Rotterdam, Utrecht, and The Hague more than half of the primary school pupils are members of minority groups.

2. Educational Policy Relating to Minorities

In the Netherlands, educational policies relating to minorities have a relatively short history and have repeatedly been revised. Four distinct phases can be distinguished (Driessen 2000; Eldering 1989; Fase 1994; van het Loo, de Spiegeleire, Lindstrom, Kahan & Vernez 2001):

1. The period before 1980 was characterized by a so-called two-track approach. The government assumed that the children of guest workers were going to stay only temporarily. Consequently, all efforts were directed toward the integration of children into the Dutch education system and, simultaneously, toward preparing them for their return to their home country. In the classroom, this meant that the children received instruction in their home language (bilingual education) as well as extra tuition in Dutch (Dutch as a second language).
2. Around 1980 the government abandoned the idea that the immigrants would return to their home countries. From then on, education aimed at preparing immigrants for their role in Dutch society. **The objective was to enable** them to become full members of society with respect to socio-economic, social, and democratic aspects, while retaining their own cultural background. A number of educational policies were designed which were specifically targeted at cultural minority groups. Among other things, this meant that schools with immigrant children were given additional resources. In addition to minority policies, a separate Social Priority Policy program aimed at improving the opportunities of native Dutch working-class children.
3. During the third phase, beginning in 1985, the Educational Priority Policy program (EPP) came into effect. This program integrated policies relating to minorities and the Social Priority Policy program. The underlying idea was that immigrant children and Dutch working-class children suffer from comparable disadvantages and that the causes of their disadvantages are very similar. The aim of the EPP was to eliminate or reduce such disadvantages.

4. At the beginning of the 1990s, it became clear that although in a broad sense some progress in the educational position of minority children had been achieved, their performance still lagged far behind that of native Dutch children. As a consequence, the government opted for a new Educational Disadvantage Policy (EDP). Its key concepts were decentralization, deregulation, and increased autonomy for the municipalities. The EDP came into effect in 1998 but has already been revised. An important alteration concerns the shift in responsibility from the municipalities to the boards of governors of schools.

3. Bilingual Models and Mother Tongue Instruction: Policies from 1970 to 2004

Bilingual education was one of the elements of the Educational Priority Policy targeted at minorities. In Dutch primary education, two models of bilingual education can be distinguished: bilingual reception models and Mother Tongue Instruction.

The **bilingual reception models** can be further subdivided into transitional models and simultaneous models (Baker 1988). Both were applied in the lower grades of primary school. In the transitional model, the children received instruction in the minority language in the third grade¹, and mixed instruction in the minority language and in Dutch in the fourth grade. From the fifth grade onwards they received Dutch instruction only. In the simultaneous model, the children for two or three years received roughly half of their instruction in the minority language and the other half in Dutch. The purpose of these types of models is twofold: On the one hand, it is expected that, with the aid of the minority language, the children will be better able to master the Dutch language; on the other hand, they are expected to attain a certain level of functional literacy in the minority language. These models were only applied in a few schools in the Netherlands, mainly in the 1980s. The languages concerned were Turkish and Arabic.

Mother tongue instruction (MTI)² was first introduced in 1967. Initially it was organized and financed by the immigrant parents themselves with or without the support of their embassies. From 1970, the Dutch government partly financed MTI. The aim of this form of MTI, which was not part of regular education, was to ease re-integration upon their return to the country of origin. After 1974 a two-fold policy in relation to the immigrants was pursued: it was assumed that many immigrants would continue to stay in the Netherlands, while the remigration idea was not given up. As a result, the aims of MTI were twofold: For future re-migrants it was considered essential to enable them to fit into the education

¹ Dutch primary schools are attended by 4 to 12-year-olds. In grades 1 and 2 play takes up a central place. In grade 3 formal instruction in reading, maths and writing starts. After the last year, grade 8, pupils move on to secondary school which they attend for 4 to 6 years.

² In the Netherlands this was referred to as 'Onderwijs in Eigen Taal en Cultuur' (OETC), which literally stands for 'Teaching in the Own Language and Culture'. Later the cultural component was scrapped and it became OET. Still later it was referred to as 'Onderwijs in Allochtone Levende Talen' (OALT) which stands for 'Teaching in Non-Indigenous Living Languages'.

systems of their countries of origin. For those staying, MTI was meant to promote integration into Dutch society. With regard to integration, the idea of strengthening minority identities became more important. From 1974 onwards, primary schools were offered the possibility of incorporating MTI into their regular program. MTI was not restricted to language instruction, but included a cultural component (e.g. aspects of the history, geography, and culture of the country of origin).

Around 1980, the government discarded the idea that the immigrants' stay was only temporary and accepted that they were to stay for good. In a policy document published in 1981 three functions were attributed to MTI:

- a) to contribute to the development of the self-concept and the self-awareness of students;
- b) to help preserve the possibility of maintaining contact with family members and friends in the country of origin;
- c) to ease the reintegration into the education system of the country of origin in case of return.

In 1983 another policy document on MTI was issued. Here the government suggested that MTI be integrated into regular education. The functions ascribed to MTI in this policy document deviated somewhat from the ones mentioned in the 1981 one. These were as follows:

- a) the development of a positive self-concept and self-awareness;
- b) to close the gap between school and home environment;
- c) to make a contribution to inter-cultural education (intended for all pupils).

Officially at least this meant that the aim of reintegration was abandoned. Instead MTI from then on aimed at the acculturation of pupils in the Netherlands who did not speak Dutch. Furthermore, the document contained a plea for a strong role of language instruction, whereas cultural instruction was transferred to the so-called inter-cultural education (which was intended for both the native Dutch and the immigrant children). It was also argued that MTI should contribute to achieving the general aims of educational policy with regard to minorities.

1984 marked an important change for MTI, as it then acquired a legal basis. Meanwhile, MTI was increasingly regarded as a means of promoting the educational opportunities of immigrant pupils. This role of MTI was strengthened by the fact that from 1986 onwards it was regarded as part of the new Educational Priority Policy (EPP), i.e. the policy for native-Dutch as well as immigrant pupils, aimed at combating educational disadvantages resulting from social, economic or cultural factors. During this period, the idea that a command of the minority language was beneficial for the learning of Dutch increasingly gained ground. Furthermore, it was also widely assumed that the teaching of the minority language would signify recognition and appreciation of the cultural identities of the groups involved and

that this would promote their emancipation. This type of MTI can probably best be characterized as a restricted maintenance model – a bilingual education model which aimed at full proficiency in Dutch and only limited proficiency in the mother tongue.

In 1991 another policy document on MTI was published. Now the emphasis was even more on linguistic arguments and the cultural component was scrapped completely. The most important proposition of this document was that minority-language instruction should be integrated into the overall language policy of the school. Its main function should be to support the acquisition of Dutch and academic advancement in general. In addition, however, MTI was meant to give access to the home culture and cultural heritage and thus promote the development of self-awareness. Greater use of the minority language within the framework of bilingual education in the first three to four grades of primary school was encouraged. In those cases in which the home language deviated from the official language of the country of origin, the home language was to be used. But from the fourth up to the eighth grade of primary education, instruction was to be given as a separate subject now mainly in the official language of the country of origin. It was suggested that MTI should be integrated into the normal school curriculum and general instruction in their own school as much as possible (children could also attend these lessons in other schools than their own, which was the case when there were only few children at a school).

In the second half of the 1990s, it became clear that the disadvantages suffered by minorities had not diminished over the years: minority students were already considerably behind when they entered primary school, and they did not catch up throughout the course of their school career. The aim of the EPP had apparently not been achieved. As far as bilingual education was concerned, it should be noted that the reception models had only been implemented at a small number of schools. Opinions varied on the effects of these experiments. This also applied to MTI. Furthermore, there was a great deal of discussion about the extent to which this kind of education was (still) useful and whether it did not in fact reduce educational opportunities and result in segregation instead of integration. As will be explained in more detail below, it had not improved performance in the regular subjects, and for half of the minority children, Moroccan children in particular, positive effects in terms of their ‘own’ language and culture were practically nonexistent. In response to these developments the Ministry of Education published a new document concerning the future of MTI. According to the ministry there were three reasons for continuing MTI:

- (a) it can enhance the emancipation and participation of minorities in Dutch society;
- (b) it can be beneficial for the Dutch economy;
- (c) it can help the interculturalization of Dutch society as a whole.

The ministry distinguished two types of MTI. In the first grades the ‘own’ language should function as a support for learning the Dutch language. In the upper grades MTI had an autonomous function as a form of cultural education. Conceived in this way, MTI was not connected with the regular curriculum and therefore to be offered after school time. An

important new aspect was that, although the ministry claimed to still support this after school MTI, it delegated the responsibility for the implementation to the local authorities.

After '9/11', the political climate changed dramatically in the Netherlands. Elections held in 2002 were completely dominated by the populist right-wing politician Pim Fortuyn, whose main theme was immigration and integration. As he claimed, many immigrants did not speak Dutch, even after having been in the Netherlands for decades, many were unemployed, and often they did not adhere to Western and liberal norms and values such as the emancipation of women and the separation of church and state. The success of Fortuyn (assassinated a few days before the 2002 elections) and his party is to be seen against the background of a growing resentment towards immigrants. Calls for assimilation instead of integration and maintenance of the minority languages and cultures have become influential (cf. Vermeulen & Penninx 2000). Now, in the first half of 2004, the Netherlands is being governed by a coalition of Christian-Democrats, Liberals, and Center-Democrats. These parties have adopted many of Fortuyn's right-wing ideas on immigration. They include the abolition of MTI as of 2004. According to the Ministry of Education priority should be given to the learning of Dutch. Another important change is that people who want to immigrate to the Netherlands have to learn Dutch in their native country and pay for these courses. If they do not pass the examination, they will not be allowed to settle in the Netherlands.

While only a limited number of children were involved in the bilingual reception models, all children of guest workers had, before 2004, been in principle eligible for the official form of MTI. In addition, Moluccan children and children of officially recognized refugees could also attend MTI. Surinamese and Antillean children, however, were excluded from MTI because the official language of these former colonies is Dutch. Chinese MTI was not subsidized either, because Chinese immigrants are not included in the official minority policy.³ Under the EPP, MTI could be attended for a maximum of 2.5 hours a week during school hours, and for 2.5 hours after school. MTI was open to first- and second-generation immigrant children. The children were to be taught in the official language (the standard language) of their (or their parents') native country. In 1995, 67,000 children enrolled in MTI. Of these, 61,000 were of Turkish or Moroccan origin, which represented 73 per cent of the total number of Turkish and Moroccan children in primary education. It was estimated that in 1998 participation dropped to 67 per cent and in 2000 to 57 per cent. In total, a full-time equivalent of approximately 1000 teachers were appointed to give instruction at 1,200 schools.

³ Very little is known about the unofficial form of MTI which is not subsidized and organized by the government, but by minority parents themselves (e.g., Chinese MTI). By definition this variant takes place after school hours and the number of hours is, in principle, unlimited.

4. The Pros and Cons of Mother Tongue Instruction

The previous paragraphs presented an overview of the aims of MTI as pursued by the Dutch government. These official aims were founded on an extensive range of arguments in favor of MTI (cf. Demirbaş 1990; Driessen 1990; Extra, Folmer & van der Heijden 1992; Fase 1987). However, there was also opposition to MTI, and the following overview lists some of the main arguments in favor of and against MTI.

Educational psychology arguments

For

- Arguments in favor of MTI are often based on the interdependency and threshold hypotheses of Jim Cummins. Broadly summarized, these two hypotheses assume that the language proficiency level in Dutch depends on the proficiency level in the mother tongue and that a certain level has to be attained in both languages before bilingualism can be assumed to have positive effects on cognitive development. Important conditions for success are, first, adequate exposure to the second language (either in school or the environment) and, second, adequate motivation to learn the second language. Insufficient development of the home language carries the risk of semi-lingualism, i.e. the child does not speak either language very well.

Against

- Both hypotheses are very abstract and have not really been described in operational terms (cf. Cummins 1991b). This makes it extremely difficult, if not impossible, to test them empirically (Cummins 1991a). Unequivocal research results to support or refute these hypotheses are not available in the Netherlands, or anywhere else (cf. Baker & De Kanter 1983; Cummins 1991a; Driessen & van der Grinten 1994; Lucassen & Köbber 1992; Willig 1985). Generally, the interdependency hypothesis suffers from a one-sided focus on language skills while the general cognitive development and the socio-economic and pedagogical family climate are ignored (de Jong, Mol & Oirbans 1988).
- Apart from this general criticism, the interdependency hypotheses cannot be proven right or wrong with regard to at least half of the non-indigenous children in the Netherlands because the (official native) language they have to learn during MTI is not their mother tongue, but a foreign (third, or even fourth) language. For all Moroccan children for example, the MTI language is Standard-Arabic. This is a formal, largely written language which bears little or no resemblance to their actual home language, in this case one of the many Moroccan-Arabic dialects or Berber varieties (Otten & de Ruiter 1993). A similar situation applies to the Kurds, who in the Netherlands receive instruction in Turkish, which is the language of their oppressors in Turkey, and also to other population groups who speak a minority language or a dialect in their country of origin.

- As time passes, minority children increasingly speak Dutch both intra- and inter-generationally (Driessen 2004). This irrevocably means that the proportion of pupils to which the above-mentioned ‘educational psychology–argument’ potentially applies, is rapidly diminishing.
- Specific conditions may apply with reference to Standard-Arabic. Educationalists point out that learning this language during the phase of alphabetization can interfere with the learning of Dutch. This is due to the fact that Arabic is written in the opposite direction (from right to left), uses different symbols, and does not register certain vowels (Schipers & Versteegh 1987).

Educational theory arguments

For

- It is often assumed that education should build as closely as possible on the knowledge and skills the pupil has already acquired. At school, a continuation takes place of the socialization process of the child, which up until that time largely took place within the family. In view of the fact that minority children speak the language of their country of origin at home and infants are still largely dominant in this language, education – at least partly and during the starting phase – should make room for the home language. The use of the home language will not only allow the learning process to run more smoothly, but will also help to bridge the gap between home situation and the (Dutch) school. Because of the fact that the school is also paying attention to the ‘own’ culture, many minority parents will feel that they are being more highly appreciated and will get the impression that the school is respecting them. In this respect MTI fulfils a psychological function towards the minority parents.
- Within this concept, it is the most important task of the MTI teacher to instruct pupils in their own language and culture, but in addition, he or she can also fulfill an important role as an intermediary between the school and the parents. With the teacher as an intermediary, the minority parents can no doubt more easily get involved in Dutch education.

Against

- It is held against this line of argument that the future of the minority children lies in the Netherlands. Even though their parents sometimes still dream about migrating back to their country of origin, it appears that the children themselves want to stay in the Netherlands. It is therefore of little use to burden them unnecessarily with extra educational content. The latter is all the more true, because precisely these children are already lagging way behind in Dutch education (Driessen 2001). If the children attend MTI during school hours, they subsequently miss parts of the regular Dutch curriculum. The lessons they have missed are only partly compensated for. There is evidence that the pupils who do not make up for these lessons do significantly less well in Dutch and arithmetic than

the pupils who do catch up on them. If the children attend MTI after school hours, often in combination with many hours of Koran instruction, then this, according to their teachers, can lead to them being so tired during Dutch education that they are no longer able to fully concentrate (Driessen 1994a).

- For Moroccan children (and in general for all children whose home language deviates from the official native language) the argument according to which MTI is necessary to bridge the gap between school and home environment does not apply. As Standard Arabic is in fact a foreign language for everyone, and given that a large percentage of the parents have little or no command of this formal, largely written language, instruction in standard Arabic might even widen the gap instead of narrowing it. Furthermore, those who do have a command of Standard Arabic largely belong to a different cultural group than the illiterate. And in view of the fact that it is the official Moroccan culture that is being passed on there is also very little room, if any, for the culture of the largest group of Moroccans in the Netherlands, i.e. the Berbers. The situation is similar for the Kurds and other cultural minority groups.
- The task of the MTI teacher is often fairly complicated, because he or she has to try and steer a middle course between different groups, each having their own demands and expectations with respect to MTI (Jungbluth & Driessen 1989). In addition, it is difficult for teachers to assume a mediating role because their command of the Dutch language often leaves a lot to be desired (Driessen, Jungbluth & Louvenberg 1988; Inspectie van het Onderwijs 1988).

Social psychology arguments

For

- Within the context of education it is necessary to pay attention to the home language in order to ensure a favorable development of the personality, a positive self-image, and to give children a sense of security and well-being. For many minority groups the home language forms one of the key values of their perception of identity. Insufficient attention to the self-image during childhood can give rise to psychological problems in later life.

Against

- There is hardly any scientific evidence supporting the assumption that MTI has the supposed psychological function. Extensive research into the self-image of children shows that non-indigenous children do not have a particularly negative image of themselves, rather, the opposite appears to be the case (cf. de Jong 1987; Verkuyten 1988; Verkuyten & de Jong 1987). There is therefore no reason for giving separate education to enhance the self-image (de Jong, Mol & Oirbans 1988).
- The concept of culture and identity underlying the pro-argument is too static. It wrongly implies that a child can only choose between one or the other culture and completely

ignores the possibility of an integration of both without a resulting split personality. And what culture should be affirmed? The culture of the parents which they in the past experienced in the country of origin, the 'official' culture in the country of origin, the dynamic mixed culture which the children are currently experiencing in the Netherlands, or an assumed culture of the future (Lucassen & Köbben 1992)? Taking all of this into consideration, it remains to be seen how MTI could possibly contribute to the development of a positive self-image.

Communication arguments

For

- Proficiency in the home language is of major importance in order to follow developments in the country of origin and to gain access to the cultural heritage of the country of origin. In addition, a good command of the home language is important for both intra- and intergenerational communication in the Netherlands as well as for communication with the country of origin.

Against

- With regard to getting access to written sources of culture in the country of origin via MTI, the main criticism is that the expectations are generally too high. The level which can be achieved via MTI is not very high (see below). For a large part of the minority children the level is probably too low to enable them to read magazines or books in the home language with any degree of ease. Besides, it is questionable whether sources really have to be read in the home language as clearly more and more such publications are being translated into Dutch. In addition, individuals can also get acquainted with their 'own' culture in Dutch, via modern means of communication such as television, video, audio equipment and computers.
- It is also argued that children should be able to communicate with their family members in the country of origin by means of writing. Here the fact is often ignored that an important part of these family members – both in the country of origin and in the Netherlands – are illiterate (Driessen 1991b; 1993) and therefore not able to read or write letters. This applies to Moroccans and Turks in particular. And again, not many children achieve a level of linguistic proficiency which enables them to read or write letters without major effort.
- As in the socio-psychological argument the fact is often overlooked that both culture and language are not static but dynamic concepts. As a result of years of stay in the Netherlands the non-indigenous languages and cultures will change (cf. de Jong, Mol & Oirbans 1988). The vocabulary, for example, is influenced by the Dutch (and also English) language. Thus the gap between the 'own' language and culture in the country of origin and in the Netherlands will probably widen.

Language-policy arguments

For

- Multi-lingualism should not be seen as a temporary problem, but as a permanent source of enrichment of a society. In that sense it has an intrinsic function. Multi-lingualism is a plus not only from a social and cultural, but also from an economic point of view. Trade and industry can greatly benefit from multi-lingualism, in particular when it comes to international contacts.
- Furthermore, by supporting MTI the government shows that it attaches importance to the languages and cultures of minorities. This can enhance their sense of self-esteem.
- Finally, via MTI the government also meets national and international guidelines on language rights.

Against

- Languages can probably be learned in a more efficient and effective way than via MTI. Evaluations, after all, show that there is hardly any direct link between MTI-participation and language proficiency. Furthermore, the number of minorities who will actually take up jobs in the international economy is only a fraction of the number of children receiving MTI. From this point of view MTI can therefore be regarded as a bad investment.
- The Dutch government can enhance the sense of self-esteem equally well, or perhaps even better – should the need for this exist – by providing regular education that has been well-adapted to the needs of minority pupils.
- As far as the (inter)national guidelines are concerned, it should be emphasized that these are only guidelines and not obligations do not give individuals a legal entitlement to instruction in a minority language (Extra, Folmer & van der Heijden 1992; Driessen 1994a).

Emancipation arguments

For

- The Dutch language can best be learned via the home language. In this way the minority child will be able to get the most out of education, and, furthermore, the disadvantage at the start of formal education is eliminated as quickly as possible. MTI in this way fulfils a crucial role in achieving equal opportunities. Via MTI the government also expresses the principle of equality of cultures, which is essential for the emancipation of minorities in Dutch society. Sometimes it is argued that MTI offers compensation for the current form of education which tries to re-educate non-indigenous children by means of subtle adaptation strategies, i.e. to adapt them to middle-class values. MTI is therefore essential to combat assimilation.

Against

- At least for the Netherlands it has never been shown that MTI can contribute to increasing educational opportunities. In view of the fact that the educational psychology arguments (see above) cannot be applied to at least half of the pupils, there is no reason to suppose that MTI also works in a facilitating fashion. Considering the actual low home language proficiency level of many of the pupils, it is unlikely that it positively influences the learning of Dutch (cf. Driessen 1994b).
- One important point of criticism in relation to MTI is that strengthening a separate, 'ethnic' identity can hamper the necessary integration of the minority children into Dutch society. It leads to segregation and is therefore anti-emancipatory (Lucassen & Köbben 1992).

5. Implementation and Practical Problems

Altogether there was plenty of discord and doubt about aims and functions of MTI in the Netherlands. Furthermore, evaluation research showed that there were major problems in relation to the practical realization of MTI. Three main problem areas were identified:

Availability and training of teachers

There was not only a major shortage of teachers, but their qualifications were also found wanting. Although the majority of teachers had undergone teacher training, this had usually taken place in the country of origin. Teaching methods sometimes strongly deviated from those generally used in the Netherlands. Thus, for example, whole-class instruction with an emphasis on imitating, learning by heart, and obedience was practiced instead of differentiated instruction with an emphasis on individual development and independent work. The Dutch-language-proficiency level of the MTI teachers was a major problem. According to the majority of school principals it was often so low that communication between teachers was extremely limited.

Limited resources and underdeveloped methods

As a result of the vague and frequently changing objectives of MTI formulated by the Dutch government, it was extremely difficult for educational practitioners to determine exactly what should be pursued. This insecurity was reflected in curricula and teaching methods. MTI-teachers were in fact relatively free to decide how they wanted to shape MTI; i.e. to interpret aims and directions, content and depth of the subject matter. Although a fair amount of material had come onto the market, teaching methods and educational resources were still underdeveloped. There was a particular shortage of educational resources suitable for the Dutch situation. The MTI methods did not connect with those used in regular education, neither with regard to contents, nor with regard to didactics. Furthermore, these reflected the multi-cultural reality in the Netherlands only sporadically, and the educational quality was well below the mark. Despite the fact that the composition

of the MTI classes was very heterogeneous, hardly any possibilities for differentiated teaching existed. Finally, considering the basic infrastructure, only half of the MTI-teachers had their own classroom; the rest of them had to sit somewhere in a corner in the hall, in the teachers' room or some other unsuitable area. And even if classrooms were available, these were mostly insufficiently equipped.

Insufficient integration with regular education

A major problem was that MTI was not embedded in and integrated with regular education. First of all there was discord about the importance of MTI and about the interpretation of its aims. Each of the groups directly involved – minority parents, MTI teachers, the Dutch teaching staff – held their own, often opposing ideas, which could put MTI teachers in an awkward situation. In addition, every now and then, those not directly involved – the media, public opinion, politicians, and scientists – also became involved in the discussion.

All in all, MTI from the very start did not stand a chance within regular education. The position of MTI was further worsened by language barriers, by deviating teaching strategies, by insufficient resources, and by the fact that MTI-teachers frequently worked at more than one school, which made it difficult for them to take part in team-meetings and consultations. For an important part, its standing was also determined by the lack of interest or even negative attitude of the rest of the school team, which saw MTI primarily, and often exclusively, as the responsibility of the MTI-teachers, and not of the school.

A growing unfavourable political climate

Of course, the position of MTI cannot be separated from the situation of minorities in Dutch society at large. Under the influence of the recent economic recession resentment about perceived inequality, unfair treatment and discrimination has taken hold. At the same time, it is becoming clear that under present conditions the Dutch welfare state is no longer affordable. This has led to increasing pressure on individuals in the most unfavorable positions. With regard to the minorities, the government now places priority on a quick acquisition of the Dutch language (and culture). This is seen as the key factor for participation in the labor market. Under given circumstances there is less and less room for 'extra' provisions such as MTI. As the educational position of Turks and Moroccans in particular is very unfavorable and does not seem to have improved very much over the years (cf. Driessen 1992a, 1992b, 1993, 2000, 2002), pressure is growing to improve their integration.

6. Evaluation Research on the Effects of Mother Tongue Instruction

Despite the fact that bilingual education (reception programs and MTI) was offered for 35 years, only very few evaluation studies were carried out in this field. Furthermore, there is a fair amount of discussion about whether the research methodology applied in the existing studies was adequate. In this respect, the situation in the Netherlands does not differ a great deal from that in other countries (e.g., Crawford 1997; Lam 1992).

Bilingual education was evaluated with regard to two possible effects: first, effects on the command of the mother tongue and knowledge of the native culture, and, second, effects on the proficiency level in the Dutch language and other aspects of the regular curriculum. The review at hand hopes to provide better insights into these effects with a focus on the proficiency level in the mother tongue. The reason for this is that in most programs the goal of retaining the mother tongue carried more weight than the role of the mother tongue as a support language. Studies were selected according to the following criteria: (1) The focus was on Turks and Moroccans; there is hardly any material on other language groups. (2) Studies pertain to children in primary education; this type of education covers a period of eight years in total, the first two are nursery education and the last six years are actual 'school years'. The children concerned are usually aged between four and twelve. (3) Finally, the studies investigate a correlation between bilingual education and home-language proficiency.

Study 1: Teunissen (1986)

Model: The study evaluated an experimental bilingual model in which, in the third grade, Turkish and Moroccan children were taught in their home language during 55 per cent of the time and in Dutch during 45 per cent of the time. In the fourth grade, the ratios were reversed. Both years were spent in ethnically homogeneous classes. From the fifth grade onwards, the children attended regular Dutch education (together with Dutch children) and additionally received 2.5 hours of MTI a week. A control group received only regular Dutch education and 2.5 hours of MTI a week.

Aim: The study investigated the effects of a bilingual-bicultural educational program for Moroccan and Turkish pupils.

Design: Longitudinal, quasi-experimental, five cohorts.

Sample: A local sample was drawn comprising a bilingual group with 70 Turkish pupils at one primary school and another group with 78 Moroccan pupils at another primary school. Both schools were located in the same city. The control group comprised 86 Turkish pupils from 20 primary schools. Children were about six to seven years old at the start of the study. When drawing samples, matches were made on starting level, age, participation in nursery education, social background, sex, and home language.

Period: 1980-1984.

Instruments: Two receptive oral tests on listening comprehension and vocabulary were used to match the bilingual group with the control group. Three tests on vocabulary, word decoding and reading comprehension were used to measure effects. These were parallel tests, i.e. Turkish or Arabic translations of existing Dutch tests or self-developed tests. Reliability computations were not made for all of the tests; the number of items involved in each of the tests is not known either. Attention was paid to concurrent validity. By means of the latter three tests, the level of comprehension, verbal fluency and reading proficiency

was tested in Turkish and Arabic respectively; writing proficiency was not tested. The tests for the matching were administered prior to the experiment (at the end of the second grade), the tests for the effect measurement itself in the third and fourth grade (i.e. during the experiment) and in the two subsequent grades, i.e. the fifth and sixth grade. Not all of the tests, however, were administered to all of the pupils in all of the grades. One Arabic test (reading comprehension) could not be administered at all because it turned out to be too difficult. On average, 30 to 40 pupils from each sub-group took part in the tests. Pupils repeating a year were tested a year later and their results were subsequently included in those of their original cohort.

Techniques: Table analysis, analysis of variance.

Results: At the beginning of the experiment, vocabulary and listening comprehension of the Turkish and Moroccan bilingual groups were not different from those of the Turkish control group. In the vocabulary, word decoding and reading comprehension, tests the Turkish bilingual group, in all grades, scored significantly higher than the Turkish control group. The Moroccan bilingual group scored significantly lower than the Turkish bilingual group in practically all grades and on all tests.

As far as the development of language proficiency is concerned, the vocabulary test for the Turkish bilingual group showed an average change in score from 14.7 to 15.7 points (SD 0.2) and the Turkish control group from 12.3 to 12.5 (SD 0.3); the Moroccan bilingual group moved from 11.9 to 14.5 points (SD 0.3). In the decoding test, scores for the Turkish bilingual group changed from 19.4 to 62.7 (SD 0.1); for the Turkish control group from 16.4 to 50.2 (SD 0.1) and for the Moroccan bilingual group from 19.8 to 24.0 (SD 0.6). It should be kept in mind that these development data pertain to a period of four years.

Teunissen concludes that the bilingual program had a clear and fairly constant positive effect on the development of the native language of minority pupils, without seriously affecting their development in the Dutch language and related school subjects.

Comments: For the Turkish bilingual model there was a control group; it was not possible, however, to find such a comparative group for the Moroccan bilingual model. Consequently, it is hard to interpret the test results of the Moroccan children. Teunissen compares the scores on the Turkish tests with those on the Arabic tests. However, it is debatable whether this comparison is reasonable. Furthermore, it is not clear exactly which pupils were tested at what moments and with the aid of which instruments. The interpretation which can be yielded from the test results is that the language development of the Moroccan pupils lags behind that of both the Turkish bilingual group and the Turkish control group. The positive effects noted by Teunissen therefore only apply to Turkish bilingual classes.

Study 2: Verhoeven (1987)

Model: The study evaluated two experimental bilingual models with Turkish pupils in the third grade of school. In model A children were first taught in Turkish but only for a period of two months. After this, they attended lessons given in Turkish in separate mother tongue classes for about half of the time, and the other half of the time they attended lessons given in Dutch together with Dutch pupils. By the end of the fourth grade, Turkish and Dutch children all received full-time education in Dutch; the Turkish children, however, had some extra hours of MTI.

In school B pupils were only taught in Turkish; instruction in Dutch was not added before the fourth grade. School A practiced a variant of the simultaneous model, and school B a transitional model. A control group of Turkish children in third and fourth grade also attended a few hours of MTI a week in addition to Dutch education.

Aim: The study investigated the effects of two models on the acquisition of language proficiency in Turkish and Dutch.

Design: Longitudinal, quasi-experimental.

Sample: Local samples in four cities were drawn. The bilingual group attended two primary schools in grades 3 and 4 (17 and 8 Turkish pupils, respectively). A control group was formed of children attending ten primary schools in grades 3 and 4 (a total of 74 Turkish pupils). The average age at the start was 6.5. When drawing the sample, matches were made on various factors such as home language, social background, participation in nursery education, age, and the number of grades that had to be repeated.

Period: 1982-1984.

Instruments: Four tests were administered to establish oral proficiency: phoneme discrimination (30 items), receptive vocabulary (108 items), productive vocabulary (80 items), sentence imitation (24 items). Three tests measured reading proficiency: word recognition (reading out words correctly), word spelling (32 items), reading comprehension (20 items). Parallel versions were developed for all of these tests: one in Dutch and one in Turkish. The tests were used to measure oral proficiency, reading and comprehension skills; writing proficiency was not included. The reliability (KR20, α) of the tests varied from 0.83 to 0.96. Attention was paid to concurrent validity and content validity. The tests were administered three times: after one month, after ten months and after twenty months. However, as a result of a number of pupils dropping out of the experiment (because of remigration and having to repeat a year), only seventy per cent of the original group were tested at the last measurement.

Techniques: T-test, multivariate analysis of variance, regression analysis, correlation analysis.

Results: At measuring moment 1, the oral proficiency levels of pupils in Turkish and Dutch were ascertained. Both the bilingual and the control group appeared to be signifi-

cantly better in Turkish than in Dutch. As far as the development of oral Turkish proficiency during the three measuring moments is concerned, it became apparent that both groups showed significant progress at about equal rates; however, the bilingual group already started with higher scores at measuring moment 1.

As far as reading proficiency is concerned, there were no significant differences between the experimental group and the control group in word recognition and word spelling; the pupils from the bilingual group, however, were better at Turkish and the pupils from the control group better at Dutch. As regards reading comprehension, there were no significant differences between the two groups in Turkish or Dutch.

Verhoeven's final conclusion was that the education received by the pupils in the control group did not adequately measure up with the background of the Turkish pupils, in view of the fact that for these pupils Turkish is still the dominant language - even after two years of nursery education in Dutch. When comparing the two groups, it became apparent that the Turkish pupils in the bilingual model were achieving better results in Turkish and more or less comparable results in Dutch.

Comments: Parallel versions were developed for each of the tests used; in general, this meant that the Dutch tests were 'translated' into Turkish. Next, the results obtained in both tests were compared. This approach is based on the assumption that the underlying psycho-linguistic operations for both languages are identical, or at least comparable; it is questionable whether this assumption is in fact justified.

Due to pupils having to repeat a year as well as due to migration back to the homeland, both groups showed an experimental drop-out rate of about thirty per cent after one year. It is not clear how this affected the average level of the remaining pupils.

One remarkable conclusion (which was not drawn in the research report) is that, taking into account the differences in scores at the start of the research, it apparently makes little or no difference for the level of Turkish whether pupils (in grade 3) are taught in Turkish for half of the time (the transitional model A), all of the time (simultaneous model B) or for merely a few hours a week (the control group). In other words: the amount of instruction does not appear to affect the level achieved.

The research does not answer a number of important questions. Thus the effect of MTI received by the pupils in the control group remains unclear, and the relevance of class sizes is not discussed: If the two bilingual classes were (much) smaller than the control group classes - as the report implies - then it is possible that effects are partly due to the fact that the children in the first group received much more individual attention from their teachers than the ones in the second group.

Study 3: Driessen, de Bot & Jungbluth (1989)

Model: MTI - the overwhelming majority of the children received MTI, but the number of hours per week varied greatly.

Aim: The study examined the correlation between MTI participation on the one hand and knowledge of the home language and culture as well as performance in 'regular' Dutch education on the other hand.

Design: Cross-sectional, quasi-experimental.

Sample: National random sample of 120 primary schools comprising all pupils in the eighth grade; 368 Turkish and 254 Moroccan pupils; average age: 12.5.

Period: 1987/88.

Instruments: Written language tests (multiple choice and open questions) in Turkish (81 items) and Standard Arabic (53 items) were used. As far as the linguistic description level was concerned, distinctions were made in the test between pragmatics, idiom, vocabulary, grammar and spelling. The level of the tests was adjusted to the abilities expected of the pupils according to those involved in MTI (MTI teachers, policy makers, educational and language experts). Pupil self-evaluation scales were used with scores ranging from (1) 'I cannot do this' to (5) 'I find this very easy' (12 items). Teachers rated pupils ranging from (1) 'definitely no command' to (5) 'definite command' (4 items). The reliability (α) of the instruments ranged from 0.83 to 0.93. Face validity, concurrent validity and content validity were studied in more detail. The tests were used to measure reading and writing proficiency. The pupil self-evaluation scales and teachers' ratings were used to measure listening comprehension, verbal fluency, reading and writing proficiency. Written language tests were used in Dutch language and mathematics (35 and 25 multiple choice items; reliability 0.87 and 0.86).

Techniques: Table analysis, correlation analysis, analysis of variance, regression and path analysis.

Results: Turkish pupils got 73 per cent of the Turkish test items right. Of the Moroccan pupils, 42 per cent did not get a single item of the Arabic test right; for the remaining 58 per cent, the average percentage of correctly answered items was 33. For Turkish and Moroccan pupils, the scores on the self-evaluation scale were 4.2 and 3.2 respectively. It should be noted that for the Moroccans the verbal command was better than the written command (3.5 and 3.0, respectively). On the teachers' rating scale the Turkish and Moroccan pupils scored 4.1 and 3.5, respectively.

In order to study the correlation between MTI participation and home language proficiency, MTI participation was indexed using the average number of hours per week during which the children over the past few years had received MTI. Because of this, it was necessary to check first whether there were any differences between the various categories of MTI participation. The correlation between MTI participation and language proficiency was linear in only a few cases. For the Turkish pupils, the maximum nominal-metric correlation (η^2) with the three effect measures (test, scale and rating) was 0.27 and for the Moroccans it was 0.26.

The following characteristics appeared to be of (some) importance in explaining the differences in home language proficiency. For the Turkish pupils they were MTI participation, age (negative), motivation, the importance parents attach to MTI, the MTI teacher working towards the aim of 'language maintenance'. For the Moroccan pupils the most important factors were language use at home (Moroccan Arabic versus Berber), the length of stay (negative), use of Dutch (negative), and the degree of contact between the MTI teacher and the pupils' parents. Speaking a Berber dialect at home in particular had a strong negative effect on the command of Arabic. The linear correlation (r) between home language proficiency and Dutch language proficiency for Turkish pupils amounted to a maximum of 0.14 and, for Moroccan pupils, -0.22 (negative). As to the correlation between MTI participation and Dutch language and math proficiency, a distinction was made between MTI during school hours and MTI after school hours. The correlation for the Turkish group was not significant while for the Moroccan group it was negative (-0.11 and -0.13). For the children who attended MTI after school hours the correlation was negative (-0.25 and -0.18 for the Turks, and -0.15 and -0.17 for the Moroccans).

The final conclusion drawn by Driessen et al. is that there are major differences in language proficiency levels. The level of Turkish appears to be fairly good, whereas the level of spoken Arabic is poor and that of written Arabic is definitely very low. The correlation between home language level and MTI attendance is weak to very weak. This also applies to the correlation with Dutch language and math proficiency.

Comments: During the construction phase, the Standard Arabic test had to be simplified significantly because a pilot study had shown that the pupils would not be able to attain the level originally aimed for; in addition, the test was produced in vocalized Arabic, which also meant a simplification.

It can be seen as a disadvantage that one of the instruments used – the language test – only measured general language proficiency and was not sub-divided into sub-tests; this makes it hard to establish the level of the pupils on certain psycho-linguistic sub-aspects.

In a comparative study in three Moroccan cities involving 117 pupils (grades 2-4; aged between 8-12) the Standard Arabic test was administered again (Bentahila & Davies 1990). 47, 51 and 78 per cent of the pupils in the second, third and fourth grade were able to answer the test questions correctly. Bentahila & Davies concluded that the results in the Netherlands were not all that bad compared with the results obtained in Morocco itself. According to Driessen & de Bot (1991), the findings in Morocco shed a new light on the low test results obtained in the Netherlands. On the one hand, the level being aimed at in the Netherlands is far too high, on the other hand, the level achieved in Morocco itself is very low.

Study 4: van de Wetering (1990)

Model: MTI. All children received MTI; the extent to which they received MTI varied widely.

Aim: The study investigated the effectiveness of MTI for Moroccan children, especially the effects of education in the Arabic language.

Design: Longitudinal, quasi-experimental.

Sample: Local sample, eight primary schools in two large cities; 447 Moroccan pupils from grades 3-8, aged between 6-14.

Period: 1983-1985.

Instruments: Decoding test (63 words), reading comprehension test I (14 multiple choice items), reading comprehension test II (13 multiple choice items). The decoding test measured reading proficiency and verbal fluency, and the reading comprehension tests measured the level of reading proficiency. Pupils were not required to produce any written work. All three tests were translated and edited versions of existing Dutch tests. The level of the tests was adjusted to the level at the end of third grade of primary school. In this study, the reliability of the tests was not established, but reference was made to studies in which the reliability (α) for reading comprehension was 0.63. Aspects of concurrent validity were taken up. The tests were administered three times, however, not always on the whole sample since the experiment had a drop-out rate of over forty-five per cent.

Techniques: Table analysis.

Results: The researcher presents the test results in relation to the number of years of Arabic-language instruction the pupils had received both in the Netherlands and in Morocco. In the word decoding test 71 per cent of the pupils with 3 or more years of Arabic education got at least 33 of the items right in the first year of the study. In the second year, the same score was achieved by 72 per cent of the pupils with at least 4 years of Arabic education, and in the third research year by 76 per cent of the pupils with at least 5 years of Arabic education. In reading comprehension test I, 70 per cent of the pupils with 3 or more years of Arabic education got at least 10 out of 14 questions right in the first year; in the second year the same score was achieved by 84 per cent of the pupils with 4 or more years of Arabic education, and in the third year by 87 per cent of the pupils with at least 5 years of Arabic education. In reading comprehension test II, 39 per cent of the pupils got 10 or more of the 13 questions right in the first year; in the following year the same score was achieved by 33 per cent of the pupils, and in the last research year by 48 per cent of the pupils.

Van de Wetering's final conclusion was that the yield of MTI in the field of word decoding and reading comprehension is relatively low, and that 3 years at least are needed to round off the decoding process. Only after 5 to 6 years of MTI can pupils be expected read out and comprehend a simple vocalized text, on the condition, however, that MTI is allowed to function under reasonably favorable circumstances.

Comments: It should be noted that no more than 54 per cent of the pupils participated in the decoding test; for reading comprehension test I, this percentage was 24 and for reading comprehension test II it was a mere 9 per cent. This was partly caused by the fact that MTI

teachers often did not allow their pupils to participate in the test because they felt their pupils could not meet the required level. Additionally, pupils who were not successful in the first or second test were not allowed to go on with the second or third test. In addition, about half of the respondents dropped out during the course of the study. Furthermore, the number of test items was extremely small and only reading proficiency was tested; no research was carried out about writing proficiency. Consequently, the results as presented in the study undoubtedly overestimate the level of the group as a whole. The interpretation of van de Wetering is not correct or at least incomplete. From re-analyses it appears that the level of language proficiency is extremely low and that this level deteriorates for each consecutive grade as the years go by.

Study 5: Aarssen, de Ruiter, & Verhoeven (1992)

Model: MTI. The pupils participated in MTI to various degrees.

Aim: The study's objective was to develop tests which could be used to assess the proficiency of individual pupils in Turkish and Arabic at the end of primary school. On the one hand, the results of these tests could be used to evaluate what they had learned during MTI, on the other hand the results provided useful information for the mother-tongue teachers at secondary schools.

Design: Cross-sectional, quasi-experimental.

Sample: The study consisted of three parts: an exploratory study, the main study (both in the Netherlands) and a comparative study (in Turkey and Morocco). The exploratory study pertains to a local sample including 23 primary schools in seven cities with 69 Turkish and 81 Moroccan pupils in eighth grade. For the main study, a national random sample was drawn from 68 primary schools and with 263 Turkish and 222 Moroccan pupils in eighth grade. The comparative study in Turkey pertains to a local sample survey at six primary schools in two cities with 276 pupils in the highest grade. The study in Morocco pertains to a local sample from six primary schools in two cities and with 242 pupils in the highest grade.

Period: 1990, 1991.

Instruments: Two tests to establish listening proficiency were applied: vocabulary and instruction comprehension (tests of whether pupils understood teachers' instructions, e.g. 'Mark the left square'). Four tests aimed to establish reading proficiency: word decoding, spelling, vocabulary, syntax and reading comprehension. In the first instance, a total of almost 300 multiple-choice items were used to determine receptive language proficiency, i.e. only comprehension and reading proficiency. In the exploratory study, two parallel versions were developed, a Turkish test and a Moroccan Arabic/Standard Arabic test. The reliability (α) of the original tests for Arabic ranged from 0.38 to 0.93 and the reliability for Turkish tests from 0.57 to 0.92. After adjustment (by means of removing about 100 items),

the reliability varied from 0.67 to 0.94. Part of the tests had been derived from Dutch material intended for six year olds. Content validity and concurrent validity were ascertained.

Techniques: T-test and correlation analysis.

Results: Test scores were converted into the percentage of items answered correctly. In the exploratory study and the main study carried out in the Netherlands, the scores of the Turkish pupils varied between 52 and 96, with scores in listening proficiency between 75 and 87, and scores in reading proficiency between 52 and 67. The word-decoding test was not included in the latter; its scores ranged from 93 to 96. In the comparative study carried out in Turkey, the scores were generally higher than those in the main study (5 to 18 test points), with the exception of reading comprehension and instruction (6 points lower). The researchers concluded that in the Netherlands pupils did reasonably well in the spelling test and fairly satisfactorily in the reading comprehension test. On the other parts, they achieved very reasonable to good scores. Furthermore, the researchers argued that the children in the Netherlands did not lag very far behind those in Turkey, the areas in which the pupils lagged behind most were spelling and written vocabulary.

The Moroccan children's scores in the exploratory and the main study varied between 24 and 81. For listening proficiency, scores were between 52 and 74, and for reading proficiency between 24 and 60. Here again, scores for word decoding were considerably higher, ranging from 81 to 79. In the comparative study in Morocco, the scores on all parts were considerably higher, i.e. 13 to 42 points compared to the main study. The conclusions were that listening proficiency was fair and that instruction comprehension was of a lower level. Few difficulties were encountered in word decoding, and the researchers also considered the level of reading comprehension to be satisfactory. However, the children did not yet have a command of word spelling and syntax and their written vocabulary was not very extensive. According to the researchers, it was possible to conclude on the basis of the differences between the results obtained in the Netherlands and those obtained in Morocco that the children in the Netherlands have a better command of the language than earlier research had suggested (in this case Driessen et al. and van de Wetering).

The final conclusion of this study was that Turkish pupils in the Netherlands have in general a high level of listening proficiency and reading proficiency in Turkish; the listening proficiency of the Moroccan children is reasonably good, but their reading proficiency is fairly poor.

In the exploratory study, the correlation between language proficiency and MTI participation was also examined. For Turkish pupils (who had attended MTI for six years on average), the correlations (r) were between -0.01 and 0.31, whereby the correlations for the oral tests were the highest. The relationships between the degree to which the children spoke Turkish at home and with friends (versus Dutch) were all weak to very weak, and sometimes even negative; the correlations varied from -0.18 to 0.28. Tests of the differences between first grade entrants and higher grade entrants (side streamers) showed that the group that had attended Dutch education from the first grade onwards in general scored

worse. For the Moroccan children the correlations between the test parts and MTI participation varied from -0.13 and 0.30. The correlation between the degree to which the pupils spoke Arabic at home or with friends (as opposed to Dutch) and the test parts was also weak; results varied from -0.16 to 0.38. In general, the differences in language proficiency between first grade entrants and higher grade entrants were small and not significant at any point, which led the researchers to the conclusion that the education received in Morocco (in contrast to educational experience in Turkey) apparently does not have an effect on the test scores.

Comments: The tests used were limited to receptive language proficiency; the pupils were not expected to actively practice language. Therefore, the researchers only succeeded in finding out something about the listening and reading skills (the easier skills), but nothing about the verbal and writing skills (the more difficult skills). In view of this limitation, it can be argued that the researchers went too far by concluding that the Turkish children had a 'good' command of Turkish and the Moroccan children a 'reasonably good' command of verbal Arabic and a 'fairly poor' command of written Arabic. If the children had been subjected to productive tests, their level would undoubtedly have turned out to be considerably lower than suggested by the researchers.

Another point of criticism relates to the fact that in three out of seven Moroccan tests the pupils did not or only just score above guessing level (four multiple choice items with on average 24 to 33 per cent of the items answered correctly). With regard to the results of the exploratory study the picture was too positive. As the research report indicates, only half of the pupils took part in some parts of the test. The remaining pupils were not allowed to participate in the tests by their MTI teachers, who felt that the tests were far too difficult and that their pupils would not be able to do them. If the teachers were right we have to assume that, if these pupils had undergone the tests, the average would have dropped considerably.

Study 6: Wagenaar (1993)

Model: The study examined the effects of an experimental bilingual model in an ethnically homogeneous class in first and second grade of primary education (nursery school) where Moroccan Arabic was spoken in the mornings and Dutch in the afternoons (for 15 and 8 hours per week respectively). Originally the intention was to reverse this in third grade, but owing to the non-availability of Moroccan teachers, it became necessary to switch, after the beginning of second grade, to Dutch education with some additional weekly hours of MTI. The third grade did, however, remain ethnically homogeneous. In fourth grade the children were divided up into various ethnically heterogeneous classes. A control group consisted of Moroccan pupils receiving normal Dutch education as well as some hours of MTI a week.

Aim: The study examined the effects of bilingual nursery education on the school careers of Moroccan children.

Design: Longitudinal, quasi-experimental.

Sample: A local sample was drawn from one primary school (bilingual model) and two primary schools (control group) all in one large city. Two times (in the bilingual and the monolingual school respectively) 30 Moroccan children from the first, second and fourth grade; two times 23 pupils who spoke Moroccan Arabic at home, and two times 7 pupils who spoke Berber. The average age at the start of the study was 4.5. In the sampling, matches were made on ethnic background, age, sex, and socio-economic background.

Period: 1987-1991.

Instruments: The sub-tests for language comprehension and language production (speaking) of the Reynell Developmental Language Test and the sub-tests for passive and active vocabulary of the Language Test for Non-indigenous Children were used. These tests were used to measure oral language proficiency; they were Moroccan Arabic translations of existing Dutch tests. No information is available about the content and number of items of the tests; and no data is presented about the reliability and validity of the tests. The tests were administered three times: at the beginning of the first grade (pre-test), at the end of the second grade (effect measurement), and at the end of the fourth grade (post-test).

Techniques: Analysis of (co)variance, regression analysis, correlation analysis, discriminant analysis.

Results: The results of the first two measuring moments are expressed in age equivalents (The test had been standardized with each test score being replaced by an equivalent age score in years and months.). In the first measurement, the bilingual group scored 3.8 years for Moroccan Arabic language comprehension and the control group scored 4.1 years (the norm is 4.5 years). There was only one significant effect of participating in the experiment with regard to the children's mother tongue: the scores of the Arabic-speaking children were 3.8 and 4.6 years, those of the Berber-speaking children were considerably lower, i.e. 2.5 and 2.4 years in the bilingual group and the control group respectively. The language production level for Moroccan Arabic was much lower, for the bilingual and control group the scores were 2.8 and 2.9 years, which is more than 1.5 years below their norm. Here too, the ethnic/linguistic group had a significant effect. The Arabic children obtained scores of 2.9 and 3.2 years and the Berber-speaking children obtained scores of 2.2 and 1.9 years. In all cases, the scores for Dutch language comprehension and language production were about 2.5 years, which is below the level of Moroccan Arabic, and 2 years below the norm. According to Wagenaar, the latter provides an argument for offering bilingual education.

In the second measurement, which took place when the children were aged 6, the bilingual group's score for Moroccan Arabic language comprehension was 5.3 years and the control group's was 3.7 years. After controlling for the first measurement, this difference turned out to be a significant one. There was also a significant difference between Moroccan-Arabic-speaking and Berber-speaking children: 5.7 years and 4.5 years versus 4.9 and 2.9 years for the bilingual group and the control group, respectively. Therefore, the bilingual group was more than six months and the control group two years below the norm. In the

bilingual group the Berber children were more than one year below the norm. The picture for language production was a comparable one although the overall level of verbal fluency was much lower than the level of comprehension. The scores for the bilingual group and the control group were 3.9 and 2.9 years. After controlling for the first measurement, this difference appeared to be a significant one. There were also major differences between Moroccan-Arabic-speaking and Berber-speaking children, but the differences were statistically not significant. In the bilingual group both sub-groups appeared to have profited from the education received, but the Arabic-speaking children considerably more so than the Berber-speaking ones. Wagenaar states that the proficiency level of the Berber children is still so low that one should have serious doubts about the use of Moroccan Arabic education for this group. She attributes this result to the fact that the home language of the Berber children is a Berber variant and not Moroccan Arabic.

Regression analysis was used to establish which factors could explain the differences in the level of Arabic. For language comprehension ethnic origin (Moroccan Arabic versus Berber) appeared to be the most important predictive factor, followed by participation or non-participation in the experiment ($\beta=-0.48$, respectively $\beta=0.28$). The same factors applied for language production, although the strength of the coefficients differed ($\beta=-0.26$ and $\beta=0.61$, respectively). IQ, sex, educational level of parents and language orientation at home no longer appeared to have a significant effect.

In the third measurement, which took place two years after the experiment was completed, the expected norm for passive vocabulary was between 83 and 92. Although the scores of the bilingual group were considerably higher than those of the control group (62 versus 47), this difference turned out to be not significant. Both groups stayed well below the norm, despite the fact that both groups had attended MTI in the third and fourth grade. The expected norm for active vocabulary was between 42 and 51; the scores of the bilingual group and control group were 18 and 17 respectively. After controlling for the starting measurement, this difference was not significant either. Wagenaar concluded that the home-language proficiency of the bilingual group continued to develop well during the period in which the experiment was run, but stagnated when the experiment was stopped. In particular, productive language proficiency appears to be sensitive to education. According to the researcher, the Moroccan Arabic language is given insufficient support in the home environment for a continued development.

As to proficiency in Dutch, Wagenaar concludes that its development was not hindered by bilingual education, although no clear positive effects were found. This conclusion is not on par with the finding that a relatively large number of children from the bilingual group were referred to special education. Discriminant analysis showed that this was mainly related to the Berber background and the very traditional values within the family on the one hand, and to participation in the bilingual model, i.e. attending Moroccan Arabic education, on the other. On this basis, Wagenaar advises Berber-speaking children (which are by far the majority of the children of Moroccan origin in the Netherlands) against participating in this type of bilingual nursery school.

Comments: It is unfortunate that there are no norms available for the tests used, which were all Moroccan Arabic translations. This makes it virtually impossible to put the results in the right perspective.

7. Summary and Conclusions

It is remarkable that in 35 years of bilingual education no more than six studies were financed in which the effect of this type of education on home-language proficiency was examined. In fact, only one study (by Driessen et al. 1989) of the effects of MTI was financed by the Ministry of Education. Probably this was due to the controversial and sensitive nature of this type of education. Like in any matters of minority policies, politicians and policy makers were, until recently, reluctant to take definitive stands on the issue (cf. Lucassen & Köbben 1992). It is nevertheless remarkable that no need was perceived for gaining insights into the effects of a considerable investment on the part of the state (in financial terms) and the children concerned (more than 10 per cent of the time spent in primary education).

All the evaluation studies reported here have methodological shortcomings. Ideally, studies should have a longitudinal design, they should adequately assess characteristics at the starting point of the experiment, study sufficiently large groups of pupils, verify all (educational) activities undertaken within the framework of the intervention and apply tests which adequately differentiate between various language modalities and psycho-linguistic sub-skills. As has been shown above, there are several methodological flaws in the studies discussed. In this respect, the Dutch situation is not peculiar (see e.g. Baker & de Kanter 1983; Birman & Ginsberg 1983; Willig 1985). Consequently, it is almost impossible to make well-founded statements on the effectiveness of bilingual programs. Statements about the level of language skills as such are somewhat less risky to make, but not entirely unproblematic either.

Taking this into account and leaving aside instructional characteristics, the following trends in language skills can be observed: The level of – both oral and written – Turkish appears to be reasonably good. As far as the level of Arabic is concerned, an emphatic distinction has to be made between Moroccan Arabic (the informal, spoken language) and Standard Arabic (the formal, written language). The command of the first is limited, of the second downright poor. This can largely be attributed to the fact that to all Moroccans Standard Arabic is a foreign language. Furthermore, the children tested do not live in Morocco, but in the Netherlands, which makes it even more difficult for them to learn Standard Arabic:

The effects of MTI and bilingual programs on the level of language proficiency do not become entirely clear. Transitional and simultaneous models appear to be more effective than MTI, which is probably related to the length of the period of instruction, the age at which it is provided, the length of stay in the Netherlands, and the home language of the children. Regarding long-term effects of transitional and simultaneous models, the results

are not promising (Wagenaar 1993). The correlations between MTI and home-language proficiency are weak at very best, and negative at worst. For the language level, factors such as home language (e.g., Moroccan Arabic versus Berber or Dutch) and length of stay (the longer the period of stay in the Netherlands, the lower the level) appear to be at least as important as the (period of) instruction. Among Moroccan children in particular, a definite loss of language seems to take place, or perhaps more aptly stated: a stagnation in language acquisition. One should probably not expect MTI to achieve more than a slowdown of this process.

In the 1980s and 1990s, MTI was expected to contribute to a higher level of proficiency in Dutch and thus more promising school careers of minority pupils. Furthermore, bilingual programs were first introduced in the Netherlands because it was argued that immigrant pupils had the right to learn their home language (also referred to as ‘mother tongue,’ ‘native language’ or ‘first language’) in order to be able to communicate with their family in that language, gain access to their own cultures, or acquire this language as an aid to facilitate the learning of Dutch. Such expectations have not been fulfilled – certainly not for the Moroccans – and cannot be fulfilled.

One major obstacle to the fulfillment of some of these aims was the absurd insistence on teaching a large group of immigrant children a language that was in fact not the language they spoke in their families. It hardly comes as a surprise that forcing Berber-speaking children to learn Standard Arabic does not help their acquisition of the Dutch language. The main question here is why this obviously illogical strategy was ever introduced and pursued over a considerable period of time.

Political aims were generally vague and changed over time, so that the implementation of an unambiguous program and its application over a longer term were impossible. Policies represented a number of compromises (and were thus partly inconsistent) and lacked a scientific foundation.

The history of the Dutch academic debate about bilingual education can be characterized as a battle between linguists on the one hand, and educational sociologists on the other. To a certain extent, the disagreement between the two scientific disciplines can be traced back to the old controversy about deficit versus difference. Linguists tend to stress the importance of learning languages as a goal in itself and as enrichment for the individual and society. Sociologists tend to emphasize educational opportunities and life chances of minorities. According to some Dutch sociologists, investing in bilingual programs was a complete waste as there was no evidence suggesting that such programs would be successful. As they argued, this was unlikely as most minorities were second or third generation immigrants who increasingly spoke Dutch at home and whose future lay in the Netherlands. With hindsight, it seems that sociologists have defeated linguists in this battle.

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